

Manifestation of Nursing Competencies of the Graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad

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Abstract

One of the provisions of the CMO stipulates that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing program must be able to apply analytical and critical thinking in the nursing practice. The nurse must be competent in the various key areas of responsibility and its respective core competency standards and indicators. The main purpose of this investigation is to determine the manifestation of core nursing competencies among the students taking Bachelor of Science in Nursing. Specifically, it seeks to determine the profile of the respondents (age, gender, civil status, year level) and the manifestation of competencies. This study utilized the descriptive-survey research design with the usage of researcher-design tool to gather data on the profile and manifestation of core nursing competencies as stipulated in the CHED Memorandum Order No. 14. The study was conducted at the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad. Using purposive sampling method, there were two hundred

(n=232) respondents who were nursing students. To analyze the data, simple percentage was used for the profile of the respondents and weighted mean to analyze the data in the determination of the manifestation of the core nursing competencies.

The results show that majority of the respondents belonged to the age bracket of 18-22 years old, female, single, and at the 3rd year level. Further, the respondents highly practiced the following: application of physical and social, natural, health science and humanities; performing safe, appropriate, and holistic care to individuals, families, population groups, and community utilizing nursing process; application of guidelines and principles of evidence-based practice in the delivery of care; practice nursing in accordance with existing laws, legal, ethical, and moral principles; effective communication in speaking, writing and presentation using culturally-appropriate language; reporting/documenting client care accurately and

comprehensively; collaborating effectively with inter, intra, and multi-disciplinary and multi-cultural teams; practice beginning management and leadership skills using systems approach in the delivery of client care; conduct research with experienced researchers; engaging in lifelong learning with a passion to keep current with national and global developments in general, nursing and health development in particular; demonstrating responsible citizenship and pride of being a Filipino; apply techno-intelligent care systems and processes in health care delivery; uphold the nursing core values in the practice of the profession, and applying entrepreneurial skills in the delivery of nursing care.

The nursing students of the university manifested the expected nursing competencies. These competencies are very significant for their

development to become professional nurses and to be a great provider of health care services to the clients or patient in any healthcare facilities in the country and abroad. In the light of the findings it is of primordial importance that the nursing competency should be integrated in all the syllabus in the professional subjects in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing curriculum to ensure maximum result in embedding the nursing core competencies to the students. Aside from that it is also important that the clinical instructors should also include the appropriate and applicable competency during demonstration in the related learning activities and community health nursing, so that they can have a real-life experience in manifesting and practice the nursing competencies.

Keywords: *Nursing education, nursing competencies, descriptive-survey, Cebu City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The nurse assumes the caring role in the promotion and restoration of health prevention of disease, alleviation of suffering and, when recovery is not possible, in assisting patients towards a peaceful death. The nurse also collaborates with other members of the health team and other sectors to achieve quality healthcare. Moreover, the nurse works with individuals, families, population groups, communities and society, as a whole, in ensuring active participation in the delivery of holistic healthcare Commission on Higher Education, 2006).

The role of the nurse is evolving as the mode of delivery of health care services has undergone major changes both locally and internationally in the past decades. In line with international trends, we are developing a health care system that provides lifelong holistic care, promotes health, enhances the quality of life and enables human development. The availability of qualified and competent health care professionals is the key to the delivery of quality health care services. As nurses play a pivotal role in the promotion, maintenance and restoration of health, we need to develop competent nurses who are able to take up extended and expended roles in the delivery of primary, secondary and tertiary care. Thus, apart from the roles of a caregiver, the nurse needs to develop competencies to take up the roles of a health promoter, educator, counselor, care coordinator, case manager, researcher as well as that of a client advocate. Hence, education programmes for preparing nurses must ensure that the students acquired the essential competencies that enable them to fulfill these roles competently and ethically (The Nursing Council of Hongkong, 2012).

Nursing is a scientific discipline as well as a professional journey. The science of nursing is based on an analytical framework of critical thinking known as the nursing process comprised of assessment, diagnosis, outcomes identification, planning, implementation and evaluation. Nurses as scientists rely on

evidence to guide their policies and practices. Central to nursing practice is the art of caring and the personal relationship that the nurse enters with the patient. Across the profession—combining the art and science, nursing focuses on the promotion and maintenance of health and the prevention or resolution of disease, illness or disability. While early education and professional practice enables nurses to conduct their clinical work, additional preparation and professional development is central to enhancing the ability to function and contribute in a rapidly changing health care environment. A continued commitment to the nursing profession requires a nurse to remain involved in continuous learning and strengthening individual performance within varied settings (American Nurses Association, 2013).

Within the context of Philippines society, nursing education with caring as its foundation, subscribes the following core values which are vital components in the development of a professional nurse and are therefore emphasized in the BSN program: Love of God; Caring as the core of nursing as to compassion, competence, confidence, conscience, commitment to a culture of excellence, discipline, integrity and professionalism; love of people such as respect for the dignity of each person regardless of creed, color, gender and political affiliation; and love of country such as patriotism to do civic duty, social responsibility and good governance and preservation and enrich of the environment and culture heritage.

In accordance with pertinent provisions of Republic Act (RA) No. 7722, otherwise known as the Higher Education Act of 1994, and for the purpose of rationalizing Nursing Education in the country to provide relevant and quality health service locally and internationally, CHED Memorandum Order No. 14 (CMO) provides the policies and standards. One of the provisions of the CMO stipulates that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing program must be able to apply analytical and critical thinking in the nursing practice. The nurse must be competent in the various key areas of responsibility and its respective core competency standards and indicators.

Therefore, the College of Nursing of a Higher Education Institution is tasked to produce nursing graduates who manifest the expected competencies of professional nurse. Thus, this investigation is conducted to determine whether the students of UC-Banilad College of Nursing is exhibit those competencies stipulated in CMO14,

Framework

This study is anchored on the Model of Professional Nursing Practice Regulation which states that the professional organization is responsible to the public and the profession to define the scope and standards of practice for nursing. The American Nursing Association (2010) established the foundational work for the profession through the ANA Leadership Package which consists of three specific documents: *Nursing Scope and Standards of Practice*, *Code of Ethics for Nursing* and *Nursing's Social Policy Statement*. these foundational documents guide the practice of nursing, frame the standards of care and reflect the patterns of professional performance in the dynamic environment of health care.

Competence even appeared in the Latin language in the form of 'Competens', which was conceived of as being able and allowed by law/regulation, and in the form of 'Competentia'; perceived as capability and permission. By the sixteenth century the concept was already recognised in English, French and Dutch; the use of the western European words 'competence' and 'competency' can be dated to this time. So it is clear that the concept of competence has quite a history, and unsurprisingly so, since to be professionally competent; being sufficiently capable and allowed to perform certain tasks, has been an aspiration throughout the ages (Mulder et al., 2006).

Although these are different fields of nursing, registered nurses will be expected to meet the essential mental and physical health needs of people of all ages and conditions including those needing end-of-life care. Some nurses qualify in multiple fields and so will be registered with us in more than one field

(Nursing & Midwifery Council. Nurses must maintain these standards for competence throughout their careers to remain on our register. Nurses must also practise in line with the most recent version of *The Code: Professional standards of practice and behaviour for nurses and midwives* (NMC, 2015).

Nursing is a caring, enabling, knowledge-based and competence-assessed profession which is dynamic in meeting the changing health needs of the society. It is committed to promoting and maintaining health; as well as to caring for the sick and the disabled as individuals, or in families, groups, institutions, home settings and in the community.

The practice of nursing is client-focused and evidence-based. It is carried out at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of health care. It functions through problem solving and collaboration with the client as well as other health care professionals to define and achieve mutually agreed health goals. The provision of holistic, client-centred care requires research-based professional knowledge and skills through the implementation of the nursing process; the adoption of a caring and responsible attitude; effective communication and interpersonal skill as well as ethical principles. The quality of care is maintained through the enhancement of professional competencies via continuous nursing education (The Nursing Council of Hongkong, 2012).

McClelland's competency approach (1973) advocated the use of the concept of competence, rather than the concept of intelligence, in testing and showed how to identify competencies by means of behavioural-event interviews (McClelland, 1998).

Competencies in this respect are acquired through training and development (McClelland, 1998) and competence is based on the description of observable behaviour or performance in situ. The definitive characteristics of the behavioural approach are demonstration, observation and assessment of behaviour. Competencies are thus the characteristics of a person that are related to superior performance in a job and can be common across situations (Delamare & Winterton, 2005).

The definition of competence in the *cognitive* approach includes all of the mental resources of individuals that are used to master tasks, acquire knowledge and achieve a good performance (Weinert, 2001). It is often used simultaneously with intelligence or intellectual abilities. The classical cognitive approaches focusing on general cognitive competencies include psychometric models of human intelligence, information processing models and the Piagetian model of cognitive development. A more narrow interpretation of this cognitive approach focuses on specialized cognitive competencies. These specialized competencies refer to a cluster of cognitive prerequisites that individuals must possess to perform well in a special area (Mulder et al., 2006).

Currently the competence-performance concept has been categorically expanded to encompass 'social' or 'emotional' competencies, in which 'competence' has replaced the original term, 'intelligence'. Needless to say, the cognitive approach to competence development is juxtaposed with the social-constructive approach advocated by e.g. Hodkinson and Issitt (1995) who formulated major guidelines to support the development of competence-based education. The guidelines aim to use competencies effectively in education by underlining essential aspects such as the high importance of mentoring, the continuous dialogue between student and mentor, the necessity of performance in practice as well as the multidisciplinary tasks the student has to cope with. In general, the social-constructive approach stresses the similarity between the competencies needed for successful performance in society (such as learning competence, cooperation, problem solving, information processing, coping with uncertainty, decision-making based upon incomplete information, risk assessment) and collaborative competence development as a synonym of social-constructive learning (Mulder et al., 2006).

As stated in the *Nursing Scope and Standards of Practice* (second edition), the public has a right to expect registered nurses to demonstrate professional competence throughout their careers. This responsibility is shared across a continuum. The registered nurse is individually responsible and accountable for maintaining professional competence. It is the nursing profession's responsibility to shape and guide any process for assuring nurse competence. Regulatory agencies define minimal standards of competence to protect the public. The employer is responsible and accountable to provide a practice environment conducive to competent practice. Assurance of competence is the shared responsibility of the profession, individual nurses, professional organizations, credentialing and certification entities, regulatory agencies, employers, and other key stakeholders (ANA, 2013).

The BSN program therefore, aims to prepare a nurse, who upon completion of the program, demonstrate beginning professional competencies and shall continue to assume responsibility for the professional development and utilizes research findings in the practice of the profession. The following are the Key Areas of Responsibility for which a nurse should demonstrate competence in: 1) Safe and quality nursing care; 2) Management of resources and environment; 3) Health education; 4) Legal responsibility; 5) Ethico-moral responsibility; 6) Personal and professional development; 7) Quality improvement; 8) Research; 9) Record Management; 10) Communication; 11) Collaboration and teamwork (CMO No. 14, Series of 2006).

An individual who demonstrate competence is performing at an expected level. The Institute of Medicine defined professional competence as the habitual and judicious use of communication, knowledge, technical skills, clinical reasoning, emotions, values, and reflection in daily practice for the benefit of the individual and community being served. A competency is an expected level of performance that integrates knowledge, skills, abilities, and judgment (American Nursing Association, 2013).

Table 1. Key Areas of Responsibility

Key Areas of Responsibility	Core Competency	Indicators
A. Safe and Quality Nursing Care	Core competency 1: Demonstrate knowledge based on the health /illness status of the individual/groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the health needs of the clients (individuals, families, population groups and/or communities) Explains the health status of the clients/groups
	Core Competency 2: Provides sound decision making in the care of individuals /families/groups considering their beliefs and values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifies wellness potential and/or health problem of clients Gathers data related to the health condition Selects appropriate action to support/enhance wellness response; manage the health problem

Core Competency 3:
Promotes safety and
comfort and privacy of
clients

- Monitors the progress of the action taken
- Performs age-specific safety measures in all aspects of client care
- Performs age –specific comfort measures in all aspects of client care
- Performs age-specific measures to ensure privacy in all aspects of client care

Core Competency 4: Sets
priorities in nursing care
based on clients' needs

- Identifies the priority needs of clients
- Analyses the needs of clients
- Determines appropriate nursing care to address priority needs/problem

Core Competency 5:
Ensures continuity of care

- Refers identified problem to appropriate individuals/agencies
- Establishes means of providing continuous client care

Core Competency 6:
Administers medications
and other health
therapeutics

- Conforms to the 10 golden rules in medication administration and health therapeutics

Core Competencies 7:
Utilizes the nursing
process as framework for
nursing

- Obtains informed consent
- Completes appropriate assessment forms
- Performs appropriate assessment techniques
- Obtain comprehensive client information
- Maintains privacy and confidentiality
- Identifies health needs

7.1 Performs
comprehensive and
systematic nursing
assessment

- Includes client and family in care planning
- Collaborates with other members of the health team
- States expected outcomes of nursing intervention maximizing clients' competencies
- Develops comprehensive client care plan maximizing opportunities

7.2 Formulates a plan of
care in collaboration with
clients and other members
of the health team

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|--|--|--|
| | | for prevention of problems and/or enhancing wellness response |
| | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accomplishes client –centered discharge plan |
| | 7.3 Implements planned nursing care to achieve identified outcomes | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explains interventions to client and family before carrying them out to achieve identified outcomes • Implements nursing intervention that is safe and comfortable • Acts to improve client’s health condition or human response • Performs nursing activities effectively and n a timely manner • Uses the participatory approach to enhance client –partners empowering potential for healthy life styles/wellness |
| | 7.4 Evaluates progress toward expected outcomes | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors effectiveness of nursing interventions • Revised care plan based on expected outcomes |
| B. Management of Resources and Environment | Core Competency 1: Organizes work load to facilitate client care | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies tasks or activities that need to be accomplished • Plans the performance of tasks of activities based on priorities • Verifies the competencies of the staff prior to delegating tasks • Determines tasks and procedures that can be safely assigned to other members of the team • Finishes work assignment on time |
| | Core Competency 2: Utilizes financial resources to support client care | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies the cost-effectiveness in the utilization of resources • Develops budgeting considering existing resources for nursing care |
| | Core Competency 3: Establishes mechanism to ensure proper functioning of equipment | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans for preventing maintenance program • Checking proper functioning of equipment considering the <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -intended use -cost benefit -infection control -safety -waste |

- | | | |
|---------------------|--|---|
| | Core Competency 4:
Maintains a safe environment | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refers malfunctioning equipment to appropriate unit • Complies with standards and safety codes prescribed by law • Adheres to policies, procedures and protocols on prevention and control of infection • Observes protocols on pollution – control (water, air and noise) • Observes proper disposal of wastes • Defines steps to follow in case of fire, earthquake and other emergency situations. |
| | From Competency 5 | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtains learning information through interview, observation and validation • Analyzes relevant information • Completes assessment records appropriately • Identifies priority needs |
| C. Health Education | Core Competency 1:
Assess the learning needs of the clients/partner/s | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering nature of learning information through interview, observation and validation • Analyzes relevant information • Competes assessment records appropriately • Identifies priority needs |
| | Core Competency 2:
Develops health education plan based on assessed and anticipated needs | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider nature of learner in relation to: social, cultural, political, economic, educational and religious factors • Involves the client, family, significant others and other resources in identifying learning needs on behavior change of wellness, health lifestyle or management of health problem • Formulates a comprehensive health education plan with the following components: objectives, content, time allotment, teaching-learning resources and evaluation parameters |
| | Core Competency 2:
Develops health education plan based on assessed and anticipated needs | |

- | | | |
|-------------------------|--|---|
| | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers for feedback to finalizes the plan |
| | Core Competency 3:
Develops learning materials for health | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develops information education material appropriate to the level of the client • Applies health education principles in the development of information education materials |
| | Core Competency 5:
Evaluates the outcome of health education | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilities evaluation parameters • Documents outcome of care • Revises health education plan based on client responses/outcome/s |
| D. Legal Responsibility | Core Competency 1:
Adheres the outcome of health education | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renders nursing care consistent with the clients bill of rights : (i.e confidentiality of information, privacy, etc.) |
| | Core Competency 1:
Responsibility and accountability for own decision and actions | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meets nursing accountability requirements as embodied in the job description • Justifies basis for nursing actions and judgment • Projects a positive image of the profession |

The student shall have an awareness of the competency-based approach in the curriculum and the core competencies under the 11 key areas of responsibility: safe and quality nursing care; communication, collaboration and teamwork, legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, research, management of resources and environment, and record management.

The student shall be able to demonstrate the competencies have an awareness of the competency-based approach in the curriculum and the core competencies under the 11 key areas of responsibility: safe and quality nursing care; communication, collaboration and teamwork, legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, research, management of resources and environment, and record management.

Specifically, the student shall: describe the health care delivery system and role of the nurse in it; demonstrate ethico-moral, legal responsibility in the care of individual family and community; demonstrate the beginning skills in the provision of independent and collaborative nursing functions; relate the stages of growth and development in the care of clients; demonstrate beginning skills in the preparation of healthy and therapeutic diets in varied client cases; explain the dynamics of the disease process caused by microbes and parasites and the environment; imbibe the core values cherished by the nursing profession such as love of God, country and people, and caring; design a plan that will focus on health promotion and risk reduction to clients; and utilized the nursing process in the care of the high risk mother and child in the family.

Due to the rapid expansion of the scope of nursing care and knowledge, nursing staff face greater responsibilities and require increasingly more skills. New specialties develop and nursing professionals rightly call for appropriate remuneration, authority and status. There is a need for more training and proficiency as the risk of legal liability increases. Nurses who set up their own nursing practice and contract out their services to clients will be dealing with contracts of mandate with all the consequences. They are self-employed, near the risk of liability themselves and are subject to the applicable labor legislation (Verschoor et al., 1997).

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this investigation is to determine the manifestation of core nursing competencies among the students taking Bachelor of Science in Nursing. Specifically, it seeks to determine the profile of the respondents (age, gender, civil status, year level) and the manifestation of competencies such as application of physical and social, natural, health science and humanities; performing safe, appropriate, and holistic care to individuals, families, population groups, and community utilizing nursing process; application of guidelines and principles of evidence-based practice in the delivery of care; practice nursing in accordance with existing laws, legal, ethical, and moral principles; effective communication in speaking, writing and presentation using culturally-appropriate language; reporting/documenting client care accurately and comprehensively; collaborating effectively with inter, intra, and multi-disciplinary and multi-cultural teams; practice beginning management and leadership skills using systems approach in the delivery of client care; conduct research with experienced researchers; engaging in lifelong learning with a passion to keep current with national and global developments in general, nursing and health development in particular; demonstrating responsible citizenship and pride of being a Filipino; apply techno-intelligent care systems and processes in health care delivery; uphold the nursing core values in the practice of the profession, and applying entrepreneurial skills in the delivery of nursing care.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the descriptive-survey research design with the usage of researcher-design tool to gather data on the profile and manifestation of core nursing competencies as stipulated in the CHED Memorandum Order No. 14. The study was conducted at the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad. Using purposive sampling method, there were two hundred (n=232) respondents who were nursing students. To analyze the data, simple percentage was used for the profile of the respondents and weighted mean to analyze the data in the determination of the manifestation of the core nursing competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section displays the profile of the respondents of this investigation, comprising of nursing students of the University of Cebu-Banilad,

Table 2. Respondents' Age (n=232)

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
18-22	130	56.03

23-27	92	39.66
28-32	5	2.16
33-37	5	2.16

Figure

Figure 1. Respondent's Age

The data contained in in Table 1 (Figure 1) shows that majority (56%) of the respondents were within the age range of 18-22 years old. This age range is the usual age of the students who are studying Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) in the Philippines.

Table 3. Respondents' Gender (n=232)

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	55	23.71
Female	177	76.29

Figure 2. Respondents' Gender

Table 2 (Figure 2) presents the data in the gender of the respondents of this investigation. It is shown that there were more female students (76%) who studied Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program in the university. Usually, females rather than males subscribe the nursing profession

Table 4. Respondent's Civil Status (n=232)

	Frequency	Percentage
Single	232	100

The data contained in Table 4 (Figure 3) shows that all of the nursing students in the University of Cebu were still single during the conduct of the survey. Under the Philippine education setting, most if not all, would study college first before going into marriage to ensure that a person has a profession that would land him/her a job that would support ones family.

Table 5. Respondents' Year Level (n=232)

	Frequency	Percentage
Level 2 (2nd Year)	46	19.83
Level 3 (3rd Year)	119	51.29
Level 4 (4th Year)	67	28.88
Total	232	100%

Figure 4.

Table 5 (Figure 4) presents the distribution of respondents in terms of year level, wherein majority of them were in the level 3 (third year).

Manifestation of Nursing Competencies

This section displays the data on the manifestation of nursing competencies as exemplified in CHED Memorandum Order No. 14.

**Table 6. Application of Physical and Social, Natural, Health
Science and Humanities (n=232)**

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.1. Integrate relevant principles of social, physical, natural and health sciences and humanities in a given health and nursing situation.	3.56	Highly Practiced
1.2. Apply appropriate nursing concepts and actions holistically and comprehensively	3.56	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.56	Highly Practiced

Figure 5. Applied Physical and Social Knowledge

The contained in Table 6 (Figure 5) shows that the respondents highly practiced applied and social knowledge, especially in integrating relevant principles of social, physical, natural and health sciences and humanities in a given health and nursing situation ($\mu=3.56$); as well as on applying appropriate nursing concepts and actions holistically and comprehensively ($\mu=3.56$). While early education and professional practice enables nurses to conduct their clinical work, additional preparation and professional development is central to enhancing the ability to function and contribute in a rapidly changing health care environment. A continued commitment to the nursing profession requires a nurse to remain involved in continuous learning and strengthening individual performance within varied settings (The Nursing Council of Hongkong, 2012).

Table 7. Perform Safe, Appropriate, and Holistic Care to Individuals, Families, Population Groups, and Community Utilizing Nursing Process (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
2.1. Assess with the client (individual, family, population group, and/or community) one's health status/competence.	3.62	Highly Practiced
2.2. Formulate with the client a plan of care to address the health conditions, needs, problems and issues based on priorities	3.58	Highly Practiced
2.3. Implement safe and quality interventions with the client to address the health needs,	3.63	Highly Practiced

problems and issues based on priorities.

2.4. Provide health education using selected planning models to targeted clientele (individuals, family, population group of community)	3.66	Highly Practiced
2.5. Evaluate with the client the health status/ competence and/ or process/expected outcomes of nurse-client working relationships	3.59	Highly Practiced
2.6. Institute appropriate corrective actions to prevent or minimize harm arising from adverse effects	3.59	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.61	Highly Practiced

Figure 6. Perform Safe, Appropriate, and Holistic Care to Individuals, Families, Population Groups, and Community Utilizing Nursing Process

The data on Table 7 and Figure 6) show that the respondents perform at a greater extent safe, appropriate, and holistic care to individuals, families, population groups, and community utilizing nursing process, based on the factor average of 3.61. This means that in the process of providing nursing care, they consider myriad of aspects to be able to provide the nursing care that is fitting to the given situation. Specifically, the respondents answered that they provide health education using selected planning models to targeted clientele (individuals, family, population group of community), as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.66 at a greater extent also. This result means that the respondents anchor on the best features of a model that articulates the nursing care needs in the existing situation. Moreover, they also answer that they formulate the client a plan of care to address the health conditions, needs, problems and issues based on priorities. Since, there are emergency situation in the practice if nursing profession, a nurse should

possess the knowledge in assessing which case must be given the first attention, to be able to save lives. Nursing is based on an analytical framework of critical thinking known as the nursing process comprised of assessment, diagnosis, outcomes identification, planning, implementation and evaluation (American Nurses Association, 2013).

Table 8. Apply Guidelines and Principles of Evidence-Based Practice in the Delivery of Care (n=232)

Indicators Provide appropriate evidence-based nursing care using a participatory approach based on:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
3.1. Variety of theories and standards relevant to health and healing	3.61	Highly Practiced
3.2. Research	3.52	Highly Practiced
3.3. Clinical practice	3.66	Highly Practiced
3.4. Client preferences	3.64	Highly Practiced
3.5. Client and staff safety	3.61	Highly Practiced
3.6. Customer car standards	3.61	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.61	Highly Practiced

Figure 7. Apply Guidelines and Principles of Evidence-Based Practice in the Delivery of Care

Table 8 and Figure 7 show that the nursing respondents answered that they usually apply the guidelines and principles evidence-based practice in the delivery of care, as indicated by the factor average of 3.61. According to the American Nurses Association (2013), the registered nurse integrates evidence and research findings into practice. Evidence-based practice and research is embodied in the work and also reflected in competencies of business acumen, systems thinking, and learning capacity. The availability of

qualified and competent health care professionals is the key to the delivery of quality health care services. As nurses play a pivotal role in the promotion, maintenance and restoration of health, we need to develop competent nurses who are able to take up extended and expanded roles in the delivery of primary, secondary and tertiary care (The Nursing Council of Hongkong, 2012). Specifically, the respondents said that they highly practiced at a greater extent in providing appropriate evidence-based nursing care using a participatory approach based on clinical practices based on the weighted mean of 3.66. This data means that in the performance of their job as provider of nursing care to the patients, their actions is based on the standards and norms to avoid erroneous or malpractice that might cause harm to the patients especially those whose condition is very sensitive. In addition, the respondents also provide appropriate evidence-based nursing care using a participatory approach based on research. This means that the research is an integral component in the nursing practice because it provides updated and supplemental knowledge in improving the delivery of quality nursing care that is responsive to the need of the patients. It is an exciting- and challenging-time to be a nurse. Nurses are managing their clinical responsibilities at a time when the nursing profession and the larger health care system require extraordinary range of skills and talents of them. Nurses are expected to deliver the highest possible quality of care in a compassionate manner, while also being mindful of costs. To accomplish these diverse (and sometimes conflicting goals, nurses must access and evaluate extensive clinical information, and incorporate it into their clinical decision-making. In today's world, nurses must become lifelong learners, capable of reflecting on, evaluating, and modifying their clinical practice based on knowledge. And nurses are increasingly expected to become producers of new knowledge through nursing research (Polit & Beck, 2004).

**Table 9. Practice Nursing in Accordance with Existing Laws,
 Legal, Ethical, and Moral Principles (n=232)**

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
4.1. Adhere to ethico-legal considerations when providing safe, quality and professional nursing care.	3.59	Highly Practiced
4.2. Apply ethical reasoning and decision-making process to address situations of ethical distress and moral dilemma.	3.60	Highly Practiced
4.3. Adhere to established norms of conduct based on the Philippine Nursing Law and other legal, regulatory and institutional requirements relevant to safe nursing practice.	3.61	Highly Practiced
4.4. Protect clients rights based on "Patient's Bill of Rights and Obligations".	3.61	Highly Practiced

4.5. Implement strategies/policies related to informed consent as it applies in multiple contexts.

3.63

Highly Practiced

Factor Average

3.61

Highly Practiced

Figure 8. Practice Nursing in Accordance with Existing Laws, Legal, Ethical, and Moral Principles

The data contained in Table 9 (Figure 8) reveals that the respondents responded that they highly practiced nursing in accordance with the prevailing law, legal, ethical and moral principles, based on the factor average of 3.61. This data denotes those professional nurses adhere to the current statutes, legislative enactment together with the ethics and morals in the performance of their job. Apart from legal steps on the basis of negligent malpractice, crime or breach of contract, action can also be taken against unethical or unprofessional conduct on the part of a nurse. This act is very important since the law stipulates that a nurse who happens to be assisting at the time that a doctor commits a criminal offence is not obliged to withdraw or to try to prevent the crime if such action could jeopardize the patient’s health. He/she is, however, obliged to report the offence to her senior or head as soon as possible. Such report will later serve as proof that she did not agree with the doctor’s behavior and that there was no common purpose between them (Vershoor et al., 1997).

Table 10. Communicate Effectively in Speaking, Writing and Presenting Using Culturally-Appropriate Language (n=232)

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
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5.1. Ensure a working relationship with the client and/or support system based on trust, respect and shared decision-making using appropriate communication/ interpersonal techniques/strategies.	3.54	Highly Practiced
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Figure 9. Communicate Effectively in Speaking, Writing and Presenting Using Culturally-Appropriate Language

Table 10 and Figure 9 presents the data on the manifestation at a greater extent of the respondents in communicating effectively in speaking, writing and presenting using culturally-appropriate language, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 3.54. This result means that they as professional nurses that they possess the ability to communicate with to their patients/client in the manner in which they would be most understood to avoid misinterpretation that might cause adverse event to the part of the patients. The registered nurse uses a wide variety of communication skills in all areas of practice. Communication is reflected in the competencies that embrace effectively communicating information and ideas in writing and verbally as well as expressing ideas clearly and concisely and inspiring others (American Nurses Association, 2013).

Table 11. Report/Document Client Care Accurately and Comprehensively (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
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6.1. Document client's responses/nursing care services rendered and processes/outcomes of the nurse client working relationship.	3.68	Highly Practiced
6.2. Ensure completeness, integrity, safety, accessibility and security of information.	3.72	Highly Practiced
6.3. Adhere to protocol and principles of confidentiality in safekeeping and releasing of records and other information.	3.61	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.67	Highly Practiced

Figure 10. Report/Document Client Care Accurately and Comprehensively

The data contained in Table 11 and Figure 10 reveals that the respondents highly practiced reporting or documenting client care accurately and comprehensively, as indicated by the factor average of 3.67. Specifically, they highly ensure completeness, integrity, safety, accessibility and security of information ($\mu=3.72$) and high extent of adherence to the protocol and principles of confidentiality in safekeeping and releasing of records and other information ($\mu=3.61$). This practice of proper documentation on the patients health status is primordially caused by their awareness on the danger and legal implication in case there will be no documentation on the patient and there is an adverse event. If this happen their profession will be put in a hot seat and possible loss of professional license if they will be proven guilty of negligence of duty.

Table 12. Collaborate Effectively with Inter, Intra, and Multi-Disciplinary and Multi-Cultural Teams (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
7.1. Ensure intra-agency, inter-agency multidisciplinary and sectoral collaboration in the delivery of health care.	3.60	Highly Practiced
7.2. Implement strategies/approaches to enhance/support the capability of the client and care providers to participate in decision-making by the inter-professional team.	3.60	Highly Practiced
7.3. Maintain a harmonious and collegial relationship among members of the health team for effective, efficient and safe client care.	3.60	Highly Practiced
7.4. Coordinate the tasks/functions of other nursing personnel (midwife, BHW and utility worker).	3.61	Highly Practiced
7.5. Collaborate with other members of the health team in the implementation of programs and services.	3.56	Highly Practiced
7.6. Apply principles of partnership and collaboration to improve delivery of health services.	3.47	Highly Practiced
7.7. Collaborate with GOs, NGOs and other socio-civic agencies to improve Health care services, support environment protection policies and strategies, and safety and security mechanisms in the community.	3.53	Highly Practiced
7.8. Participate as a member of a quality team in implementing improvement opportunities.	3.41	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.55	Highly Practiced

Figure 11. Collaborate Effectively with Inter, Intra, and Multi-disciplinary and Multi-Cultural Teams

The data contained in Table 11 shows that the respondents highly practiced collaboration effectively with inter, intra and multi-cultural teams. Specifically, the respondents said that they coordinate the tasks/functions of other nursing personnel (midwife, BHW and utility worker). During the community health-nursing course, the nursing students were exposed to the patients at the Barangay Health Center and the adopted community. During this exposure, the students were given the change to work with Barangay Health Workers (BHW) and utility workers. Further, they were also exposed to the work of midwives in the hospital and birthing centers during their Related-Learning Exposure. Moreover, they also said that they participate as a member of a quality team in implementing improvement opportunities. Interprofessional is related to nursing competency since it refers to the shared relationship among individuals, groups, and organizations from different disciplines. The synergies created through groups, committees, projects that comprise individuals from different disciplines; the impact of teamwork (American Nurses Association, 2013).

Table 13. Practice Beginning Management and Leadership Skills using Systems Approach in the Delivery of Client Care (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
8.1. Participate in the development and improvement of policies and standards regarding safe nursing practice and relevant to human resource management.	3.59	Highly Practiced
8.2. Manage resources (human, physical, financial, time) efficiently and effectively.	3.57	Highly Practiced
8.3. Apply management and leadership principles in providing direction to manage a community/village-based.	3.58	Highly Practiced
8.4. Use appropriate strategies/approaches to plan community health programs and nursing service.	3.66	Highly Practiced
8.5. Supervise the implementation of the nursing component of the health services/programs.	3.60	Highly Practiced
8.6. Ensure that all nursing personnel adhere to standards of safety, bioethical principles and evidence based nursing practice.	3.56	Highly Practiced

8.7. Evaluate specific components of health programs and nursing services based on parameters/criteria.	3.62	Highly Practiced
8.8. Maintain a positive practice environment.	3.67	Highly Practiced
8.9. Participate in the planning and implementation of staff nursing support staff.	3.58	Highly Practiced
8.10. Evaluate performance of nursing support staff using a standard evaluation tool.	3.55	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.60	Highly Practiced

Figure 12. Practice Beginning Management and Leadership Skills Using Systems Approach in the Delivery of Client Care

Table 14 (Figure 12) displays the result on the respondents' manifestation of practicing beginning management and leadership skills using system approach in the delivery of client care. The factor average of 3.60 denotes that they highly practiced system approach in rendering client care. Furthermore, they highly practiced the maintenance of a positive practice environment, based on the weighted mean of 3.67 and evaluate performance of nursing support staff using a standard evaluation tool. Ensuring that all the nurses possess the competence in providing quality client, is of primordial concern in the health care arena. So, there should be effective leadership that will enable the nurse to be trained and learned. The clinical competencies in nursing education provide the foundation for the development of competencies in nursing practice (Gilje, Klose & Birger, 2007).

Table 14. Conduct Research with Experienced Researchers (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
9.1. Participate in preparing a research proposal complying with the ethical principles in nursing research.	3.54	Highly Practiced
9.2. Conduct a research study as a member of a research team.	3.58	Highly Practiced
9.3. Determine if the research problems/questions, learning outcomes and/or hypotheses are clearly and logically linked to the research purpose, concepts and relationships, and propositions generated from the study framework.	3.46	Highly Practiced
9.4. Analyze if the conceptual framework the summary of review of related literature, research design, and data analysis procedure are logically linked with the research purpose, problems/questions, and hypotheses.	3.58	Highly Practiced
9.5. Establish if the interpretation, implications, and recommendations are consistent with the results considering the limitations of the study.	3.57	Highly Practiced
9.6. Analyze the research study/report for adherence to standards of writing mechanics, ethical principles and guidelines in all phases of the research study.	3.64	Highly Practiced
9.7. Present the research study conducted in partnership with a research team.	3.68	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.58	Highly Practiced

Figure 13. Conduct Research with Experienced Researchers

The data contained in Table 14 shows that the respondents said that they highly practiced the conduct of research with experienced researchers ($\mu=3.58$). Specifically, the respondents reported that they present their research study conducted in partnership with a research team ($\mu=3.68$) and determine if the research problems/questions, learning outcomes and/or hypotheses are clearly and logically linked to the research purpose, concepts and relationships, and propositions generated from the study framework ($\mu=3.48$). This data indicates that the respondents had experienced conducting research wherein they worked and journey with an experienced mentor who possess the adequate knowledge on the rigors of conducting research work.

Table 15. Engage in Lifelong Learning with a Passion to Keep Current with National and Global Developments in General, Nursing and Health Development in Particular (n=232)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
<i>To keep current with national and global developments in general, and nursing and health development in particular:</i>		

10.1. Assume responsibility for lifelong learning, own personal development and maintenance of competence.	3.62	Highly Practiced
10.2. Demonstrate continued competence and professional growth.	3.65	Highly Practiced
10.3. Engage in advocacy activities to influence health and social care service policies and access to services.	3.69	Highly Practiced
10.4. Model professional behavior.	3.68	Highly Practiced
10.5. Engage in advocacy activities to deal with health related concerns and adopts policies that foster the growth and development of the nursing profession.	3.68	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.66	Highly Practiced

Figure 14. Engage in Lifelong Learning with a Passion to Keep Current with National and Global Developments in General, Nursing and Health Development in Particular

Table 15 shows that the respondents highly engaged or practiced lifelong learning to keep current with national and global developments in general, and nursing and health development as evidenced by the factor average of 3.66. In particular, they engaged in advocacy activities to influence health and social care

service policies and access to services based on the weighted mean of 3.69 at a greatest extent. Loving your job and patients, is of primordial important in the nursing profession. As an integral part of the holistic development for nursing students, the school should expose the students to advocacy activities, especially on the community extension activities. In this manner, the students will be given the chance to development their behavior in community service in the area of health care that this kind of learning will be carried out all their life. On the other hand, the students answered that they assume responsibility for lifelong learning, own personal development and maintenance of competence ($\mu=3.62$) at the greatest extent. This means that the nursing student would continuously seek learning even after they finished their baccalaureate degree so that they will be updated on the new trends in the nursing practice.

Table 16. Demonstrate Responsible Citizenship and Pride of Being a Filipino

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
11.1. Exemplify love for country in service of the Filipinos.	3.64	Highly Practiced
11.2. Customize nursing interventions based on Philippine culture and values.	3.69	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.66	Highly Practiced

Figure 15. Demonstrate Responsible Citizenship and Pride of Being a Filipino

The factor average of 3.66 denotes that the respondents demonstrated to be responsible citizenship and pride in being a Filipino. This means that the respondents possess the heart to become a model Filipino citizen wherever they would be in the future since Filipinos nurses are in demand all through the world. Furthermore, the weighted mean of 3.69 denotes that they customize nursing interventions based on Philippine culture and values. The also exemplified love for country in service of the Filipinos at a higher extent. Applying the nurturing and caring customs and tradition of Filipinos in the nursing makes Filipinos nurses to be an ordinary healthcare professional in the globe, since these behaviors are not being practiced

by other nurse of different nationalities. The Filipino way of caring the patient applies the love to mankind without racism.

Table 17. Apply Techno-Intelligent Care Systems and Processes in Health Care Delivery

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
12.1. Use appropriate technology to perform safe and efficient nursing activities.	3.65	Highly Practiced
12.2. Implement system of informatics to support the delivery of health care.	3.69	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.67	Highly Practiced

Figure 16. Apply Techno-Intelligent Care Systems and Processes in Health Care Delivery

Table 17 reveals that the respondents continuously apply techno-intelligent care systems and processes in health care delivery at a greatest extent based on the factor average of 3.67. In the delivery of care, the respondents answered that highly practiced the usage of appropriate technology to perform safe and efficient nursing activities ($\mu=3.65$) and implement system of informatics to support the delivery of health care ($\mu=3.67$). Nowadays, technology plays a very vital role in improving the healthcare industry. Therefore, it is very important healthcare facilities should use appropriate technological systems and gadget to ensure efficient and accurate provision of services to the patients, especially in the nursing aspect.

Table 18. Uphold the Nursing Core Values in the Practice of the Profession

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
13.1. Demonstrate caring as the core of nursing, love	3.75	Highly Practiced

God, love of country and love of people.		
13.2. Manifest professionalism, integrity and excellence.	3.66	Highly Practiced
13.3. Project the positive professional image of a Filipino nurse.	3.70	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.70	Highly Practiced

Figure17. Uphold the Nursing Core Values in the Practice of the Profession

The data contained in Table 18 (Figure 17) shows that at the greatest extent, the respondents uphold the nursing core values in the practice of the profession, as indicated by the factor average of 3.70. Specifically, the respondents, also at a greatest extent demonstrated the caring as the core of nursing, love God, love of country and love of people ($\mu=3.75$), manifest professionalism, integrity and excellence ($\mu=3.66$) and project the positive professional image of a Filipino nurse ($\mu=3.70$). These results can be inferred that the upholding the nursing core values profession is very important since in providing care to the patients, it entails extra love towards other human being.

Table 19. Apply Entrepreneurial Skills in the Delivery of Nursing Care

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
14.1. Identify opportunities for entrepreneurial nursing practice.	3.66	Highly Practiced
14.2. Apply strategic interventions to address health-related concerns of individuals, families, communities and population groups to any health care setting.	3.61	Highly Practiced
Factor Average	3.64	Highly Practiced

Figure 18. Apply Entrepreneurial Skills in the Delivery of Nursing Care

Lastly, Table 19 (Figure 18) shows that the respondents applied entrepreneurial skills in the delivery of nursing care ($\mu=3.64$). Specifically, the respondents answered that at the highest extent they identify opportunities for entrepreneurial nursing practice ($\mu=3.66$). Aside from having knowledge in nursing, they also manifested the competency of looking into business opportunities in the area of nursing.

Moreover, they also highly apply strategic interventions to address health-related concerns of individuals, families, communities and population groups to any health care setting ($\mu=3.61$). This data denotes that that the respondents have the heart to be mindful of taking appropriate measures to address the various problems and challenges pertaining to health.

Conclusion

The nursing students of the university manifested the expected nursing competencies. These competencies are very significant for their development to become professional nurses and to be a great provider of health care services to the clients or patient in any healthcare facilities in the country and abroad.

Translational Research

In the light of the findings, it is of primordial importance that the nursing competency should be integrated in all the syllabus in the professional subjects in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing curriculum to ensure maximum result in embedding the nursing core competencies to the students. Aside from that it also important that the clinical instructors should also include the appropriate and applicable competency during demonstration in the related learning activities and community health nursing, so that they can have a real-life experience in manifesting and practice the nursing competencies.

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